

IMPORTANCE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN PREPARING CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8086438>

Abstract. *This article focuses on the importance of preschool education in preparing children for school education. At the same time, he reflects on the priority of the main tasks and goals.*

Keywords: *pre-school education, continuous education, pre-school training, school education, Law on «Education».*

The stage of preschool education is the most important and responsible stage of continuous education, where the foundations and foundations of child upbringing and education are formed. The main tasks of preschool education are to educate children in the spirit of the nation's rich national, cultural, historical heritage and spiritual and moral traditions, to form children's feelings of national patriotism, to form preschool children's need for education, and their inclination to study. regular preparation for the educational process, development of children's thinking, formation of skills of independent and free expression of one's opinion, provision of physical and mental health of children. At this stage, the issue of preparing children for school education is one of the most pressing issues. With this in mind, today fundamental changes are being made in the field of preschool education in our country, in the field of preparing children for school education.

In the field of pre-school education, the works carried out by the active initiative of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, decrees and decisions are gaining importance. Establishment of the Ministry of Pre-School Education, the President's Resolution No. 2707 (29 December 2016) "On Measures to Further Improve the Pre-School Education System in 2017-2021", "Pre-school Education Decree No. PF-5198 (September 30, 2017) "On measures to radically improve the management of the education system" of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the activities of preschool educational institutions "Decision No. 528 (July 19, 2017), the adoption of official documents such as "Concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" is of particular importance in improving the quality and efficiency of education in the preschool education system. taking place.

Preparing children for school education has its own set of criteria. In this process, preparing children for school physically, intellectually, mentally, willfully and spiritually is one of the foundations that ensure their stress-free education, continuity and effectiveness of education.

Scientific and methodological support of future pedagogues and their professional training are among the main issues in improving the process of preparing preschool children for school education. In particular, children's physical characteristics, anthropometric indicators, mental-willing aspects, mental readiness for school are considered important for their intellectual and physical adaptation to school education, learning subjects without strain.

In preparing children for school, it is important to rely on methodical knowledge in this regard, to be based on a clear system and sequence.

The main goal and driving force of the reforms implemented in the republic is the harmonious development of a person in all aspects, the creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for the realization of personal interests, and the change of outdated patterns of thinking and social behavior. The formation of an excellent system of personnel training based on the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal values, on the basis of the achievements of modern culture, economy, science and technology, is an important condition for the development of Uzbekistan.

Pre-school education ensures the healthy, all-round development of a child, instills in him a desire to study, and prepares him for regular education. Preschool education is carried out in state and non-state preschool education organizations and families until the child reaches the age of 6-7. Neighborhoods, public and charitable organizations, and international funds actively participate in the realization of the goals and tasks of preschool education.

To develop preschool education, it is necessary to implement the following:

- priority training of qualified educators and pedagogues;
- search and implementation of effective psychological and pedagogical methods of preschool education;
- providing organizational, psychological, pedagogic and methodical upbringing of children in the family;
- creation and production of modern educational manuals, technical tools, toys and games;
- creating conditions for morally and morally educating children of preschool age based on the rich cultural and historical heritage of the nation and universal values;
- to create the opportunity to select programs of various options for various types of preschool education organizations, to provide qualified consulting services on all issues of preschool education;
- aims to develop a mechanism for supporting and developing the network of pre-school education and health care organizations.

Also, in the "Regulation on Preschool Education" in the Republic of Uzbekistan, special emphasis is placed on preschool education, preschool education is the initial type of continuous education system, and "Education on" law and the existing requirements therein.

The main tasks of preschool education are defined as:

- educating children intellectually, spiritually and morally on the basis of the nation's rich national, cultural and historical heritage and universal values;
- formation of national pride and patriotism in children;
- forming the need for education in children of preschool age, the desire to study, and preparing them for the regular educational process;
- development of children's thinking, formation of skills of independent and free expression of their thoughts;
- aims to ensure children's physical and mental health.

Pre-school educational organizations are organized taking into account the demographic, socio-economic and other characteristics of the regions, organization and termination of preschool educational organizations are carried out in accordance with the law.

As in every field, in the preschool education system, persons with relevant education, professional training and high moral qualities have the right to engage in pedagogical activities.

Training, retraining and upgrading of pedagogical personnel, maintaining the quality of the profession at a competitive level is ensured by the competent state bodies for education management.

The educational and pedagogical tasks of the pedagogic staff of preschool education organizations are determined by the Ministry of Preschool Education based on the state requirements for the type of preschool education. It provides conditions for the introduction of advanced pedagogical and information technologies, new programs recommended by experts, methodical manuals, and didactic materials.

The goal of preschool education is to form a child's personality in a healthy and mature manner, prepared for school in accordance with the State requirements for the education of preschool children.

As a conclusion of our opinion, we can say that it is permissible to pay close attention to the pre-school education system and its activities for preparing children for school. In this regard, it is important to make the tasks of preschool education more relevant, that is, to educate children in the spirit of the rich national, cultural, historical heritage and spiritual and moral traditions of the people, to form children's sense of national patriotism, the need for education in preschool children, to study. it is necessary to form aspirations and prepare them regularly for the educational process, to develop children's thinking, to form the skills of independent and free expression of their thoughts, to ensure children's physical and mental health. All these efforts mean that we are not indifferent to the fate of our children, who are the owners of the future generation. It is also a sign that we need to create conditions for them to get meaningful education from childhood in order to build New Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Alimova Madinaxon Iskanqar qizi, Egamberdiev N.B, UZBEK WOMEN IN DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 1 JANUARY 2023. 17-25-p.
2. Alimova M. I., Egamberdiev N. B., THE ROLE OF SCIENCE FROM CHILDHOOD AS A CASE STUDY THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 1 JANUARY 2023. 26-34p.
3. Dilshoda Jalilova Ural qizi. BO‘LAJAK BOSHLANG‘ICH SINIF O‘QITUVCHILARIDA AXBOROT KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MASALASINING AHAMIYATI. RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR DAVRIDA TILLARNI INTENSIV O‘QITISHNING PSIXOLOGIK- PEDAGOGIK JIHATLARI RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI. 2023-yil 2-iyun (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993607>)
4. Dilshoda Jalilova Ural qizi, Shahzoda Jamilova. BO‘LAJAK BOSHLANG‘ICH SINIF O‘QITUVCHILARINI INNOVATSION FAOLIYATGA TAYYORLASHNING E‘TIBORLI JIHATLARI. YANGILANAYOTGAN O‘ZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTIDA IQTISODIY FANLARNI O‘QITISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI mavzusida gi respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi. 2023-yil 16-iyun. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=%222181-3337

5. Jalilova D.U. Psychological And Technological Features of Increasing the Efficiency of Educational Activity of Talented Students in Presidential Schools. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices ISSN NO: 2770-2367 (<https://zienjournals.com>).
6. Madinakhon Alimova Iskandar qizi. WASTEWATER POLLUTION AND ITS EFFECTS ON HUMAN HEALTH. «ҚИШЛОҚ ВА СУВ ХЎЖАЛИГИНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ МУАММОЛАРИ» *мавзусидаги анъанавий XXII – ёш олимлар*, www.ttiame.uz магистрантлар ва иқтидорли талабаларнинг илмий-амалий анжумани. Тошкент - 2023 йил www.ttiame.uz
7. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining qarori, 19.07.2017 yildagi 528-son.
8. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining qarori, 08.05.2019 yildagi PQ-4312-son